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**ADOLESCENTS' PERCEPTION OF SEX EDUCATION AND
UNDESIRABLE SEXUAL BEHAVIOURS IN FCT COLLEGE OF
EDUCATION (FCT COE) ZUBA, NIGERIA.**

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Abstract

This study examined the adolescents' perception of the role of sex education in preventing undesirable sexual behaviours in the life of the youths and the counselling implications. The population of the study consisted of 3,000 students out of which 300 students were randomly selected as sample for the study. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled 'Sexual Behaviour Descriptive Questionnaire' (SBDQ). Two research hypotheses formulated for the study were tested at a 0.05 level of significance. The data were analysed using frequency counts, simple percentages, and t-test statistics. The results of the study revealed that students of FCT COE Zuba were unanimous in their perception of the types of sexual behaviours prevalent amongst adolescents, irrespective of gender differences. It is also clear that sex education programmes carefully designed and implemented will bring about significant and positive changes in adolescent sexual behaviours. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended among other things that sex education should be introduced as a compulsory course in the curricula of all higher institutions of learning in Nigeria.

Keywords: Adolescents, Sex Education, Sexual behaviours Gender difference, Sex, Sexuality.

Introduction

Adolescence is a phase in life where a person is neither a child nor an adult. Adolescence is saddled with certain developmental problems, (Denwigwe & Akpama, 2013). They further revealed that depending on how these problems are handled, the individuals may become well-adjusted or maladjusted. Adolescence is a bridge between an asexual child and a sexual adult. During this period, the lives of both males and females become wrapped in sexuality. Adolescence is a time of sexual exploration and incorporating sexuality into one's identity. Adolescents have an almost insatiable curiosity about the mystery of sex. They wonder whether they are sexually attractive, how to behave sexually, and what the future holds for their sexual lives. Adolescent sexuality refers to sexual feelings, behaviour, and developments in adolescents. Sexuality is often a vital aspect of the teenagers' lives. In humans, mature sexual desires usually begin to appear with the onset of puberty. Sexual expression can be seen in the form of masturbation, sex with a partner, close body contact, and romance (Santrock, 2005). Generally, sexual activity is associated with many risks. These include unwanted pregnancies, abortions, and sexually transmitted diseases like HIV, Syphilis, Full-blown AIDS, Gonorrhoea, Pelvic Inflammatory Diseases (PID), and so on.

Olowonirejuaro in Adeoye and Olowonirejuaro (2008) posits that most times adolescents get involved in sexual relationships ill-prepared and uncensored. Hence most times they are faced with unfavourable consequences of such uncensored acts. He further explains that such sexual relations and activities among adolescents are the major causes of indiscipline. Most problems parents have with adolescents have to do largely with their sex life.

Isangedihi (1994) in Adeoye and Olowonirejuaro (2008) pointed out that Nigerian adolescents are being increasingly exposed to modernization as they read about sex in novels, books, magazines, newspapers, and on the net. They are also exposed daily to various types of pornographic films and advertisements on television and in their various discussions these feature greatly. Although these may be serving as sources of needed information, they are also capable of greatly arousing and keeping adolescents'

interest in sex matters if not properly guided can impact negatively on adolescents.

Santrock (2005) identified the following five sexual characteristics of adolescents which include:

- ✓ Sexually naïve,
- ✓ Sexually unassured
- ✓ Sexually unadventurous
- ✓ Sexually driven, and
- ✓ Sexually competent.

Young people today according to Adesioye (1996) start sex before marriage unlike in the olden days. This has led to some facing more risks of HIV, Aids, unwanted pregnancies, abortion, and loss of life. When the youths have started to experiment on these sexual activities on their own, they disobey their parents or guardians, attend social parties, and night clubs. Hence, there is the need to for a comprehensive sexual education early enough. This will enable the society to prepare the adolescent for a healthy sexual life. Sexuality education is the process of acquiring information, forming attitudes and, beliefs about sex, sexual identity, and sexual behaviours. This is desired to replace ignorance, anxiety, fear, secrecy, and guilt with knowledge and understanding, openness and nationality (Akinade & Sulaiman, 2005).

Sexuality education is also about developing skills such that adolescents can make good and informed choices about their sexual lives or behaviours. It is in light of these that this research is being conducted to see at the end of the study the importance of Sexuality education as perceived by the youths and its subsequent influence on the sexual behaviour of the adolescents.

Statement of the problem

Sexuality is often a vital aspect of the lives of the teenagers. The sexual behaviour of an adolescent is more often than not influenced immensely by his or her own culture,

norms, and mores, his/her sexual orientation and the issue of social control such as age of consent laws(en.wikipedia.org). Understanding how, why, and when an adolescent decides to initiate sex or abstain from sex, and why a particular type of sexual behaviour will be preferred, is critical for the development of more effective sex education programmes or public health campaigns directed towards delaying or preventing adolescents' undesirable or desirable sex behaviours. According to Bonnie and Yana (2009), many studies examining adolescent sexual attitudes and behaviour have been within the context of decision-making models. These models assert that engagement in any behaviour including sexual behaviour entails the weighing of perceived positive and negative outcomes. Many factors may put adolescents at risk for becoming sexually active. Akintola & Adewumi (1996) observed that parents only prefer to say little about the dangers of having sex, especially premarital sex, but they fail to discuss the physical and physiological changes that take place during adolescence. This is the reason why the youths oftentimes get their directions and sense of values on sex and sexuality from mass media, peers, and uncensored information which could have negative effects on them. This study therefore finds it necessary to investigate the adolescents' perception of sex education as a panacea to adolescent undesirable sexual behaviours and to also consider the counselling implications.

Specific Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to:

- (a) investigate the types of adolescent sexual behaviours prevalent among students in FCT COE Zuba
- (b) examine any significant difference in the types of sexual behaviours prevalent among the youths based on gender.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested in the study:

Hypothesis 1 There is no significant difference in the types of adolescent sexual behaviour as expressed by male and female students of FCT COE Zuba, Abuja

Hypothesis 2 There is no significant difference in the types of adolescent sexual behaviour as expressed by students after being exposed to sex education.

Methodology

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 3000 male and female adolescent students of FCT COE Zuba, Abuja out of which 300 were randomly selected as sample from three levels/parts. These are first (1st) year, second (2nd) year and final(3rd) year students. From each arm of the 3 levels, 100 students were randomly selected bringing the total respondents to 300 students. The respondents were appropriately guided by five research attendants trained by the researchers to fill the questionnaires the right way. The 300 questionnaires were correctly filled and returned; hence, 300 students participated in this study. This represents 100% return rate. The research instrument used for this study was titled 'sexual Behaviour Descriptive Questionnaire' (SBDQ), designed, and developed by the researchers. It has two sections. Section A comprises the personal data of the respondents while section B contains 30 items with a response format of strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. The instrument was validated by 5 professional counsellors in the Department of Counselling Education of the University of Abuja and FCT College of Education, Zuba Abuja respectively. The experts made corrections and useful suggestions. The modified copy adjudged adequate for the study by the experts was used to conduct this study. A test re-test method of reliability was adopted to determine the reliability of this instrument. Questionnaire was administered twice within an interval of three weeks to another category of respondents. Another set of respondents was involved. The two sets of

scores were correlated using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. A co-efficient value of 0.71 was obtained This was adjudged high enough by the researchers and therefore suitable for this study.

Results

In analysing the data collected for the study, the respondents' personal data were analysed using frequency counts, and simple percentages while the t-test was used to analyse the research hypothesis formulated.

The various results obtained were presented based on the hypotheses that were formulated for the study. The personal data of the respondents showed that based on sex, 180 (60%) of the respondents were females while 120 (40%) were males. Based on age, 260 (87%) of the respondents fell between 15 and 20 years while only 40 (13%) of the respondents fell within 21 years and above.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the types of adolescents' undesirable sexual behaviour prevalent amongst FCT COE Zuba students based on gender.

Table 1: T-test statistics of students' perception of the type of adolescents' sexual behaviour prevalent amongst students based on their sex (gender).

Sex	No. of Cases	\bar{X}	Sd	Df	t-cal	t-crit
Male	120	25.08	2.53	197	1.08	1.96
Female	180	25.53	1.69			

*Significant, $P < 0.05$

Table 1 shows a calculated t-value of 1.08 and a critical t-value of 1.96. Since the calculated t-value is less than the critical t-value at 0.05 alpha level, the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that the male and female students of FCT COE, Zuba are not significantly different in their expression of types of adolescents' undesirable sexual behaviour. Based on this result, the null hypothesis is accepted, $t(df=197) = 1.08 > 0.05$.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference in the type of adolescent undesirable sexual behaviour as expressed by students after being exposed to sex education programmes.

Table 2: t-test statistic of students' perception of the influence of sex education on the types of adolescents' sexual behaviour

Sex	No. of Cases	\bar{X}	Sd	Df	t-cal	t-crit
Male	120	75.76	.635	298	21.02*	1.96
Female	180	57.30	16.65			

*Significant, $P < 0.05$

Table 2 shows that the calculated t-value of 21.02 is greater than the critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 alpha levels. Hence, there is a significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the influence of sex education on the types of adolescents' undesirable sexual behaviour. Based on this result, the null hypothesis is rejected, $t(df=298) = 21.02, p < 0.05$.

Discussion of findings

The findings from the study revealed that the students in FCT College of Education Zuba, irrespective of their sex, are similar in their perception of the type of 'adolescent' sexual behaviour prevalent among the students. Adolescents' sexual behaviour varies greatly. It ranges from kissing and petting to non-coital behaviour such as oral sex and anal sex to vaginal intercourse., flirting, dating, sexual dialogue, and uncensored dressing. The study reveals that the expression of these sexual behaviours among students is the same irrespective of students' gender differences. However, the findings slightly disagree with the findings of Bonnie and Yana (2009) who carried out a study on adolescents' social attitudes and behaviours, and discovered that adolescents' sexual behaviour, rates of initiation and patterns of engagement in sexual activities depend largely on age, gender and race or ethnicity. However, the study is in agreement with the study O'Sullivan and colleagues (2008) titled 'Adolescent sexual functioning and behaviour; gender similarities and differences' and found no significant gender differences in expression and prevalence of sexual behaviour and dysfunctions. Hypothesis two stated that there were no significant differences in the types of adolescent sexual behaviour as expressed by students after being exposed to sex education programmes.

The findings from the study further revealed that this null hypothesis was rejected. This confirms and establishes the importance or the effect of sex education on adolescents' positive sexual behaviour. The finding corroborates the submission by Schuster, Berry, and Kanouse (2002) who carried out an indebt study on understanding the sexual behaviour of adolescents and discovered significant changes in the student's attitudes and perceptions about participating in sexual activities, behaviours, and condom use before and after exposure to sex education programmes. For instance, they found that condom use increased after the programme began as the percentage of those who used condoms for vaginal intercourse in the year before the

survey, increased significantly from 37% before the programme to 50% after the programme was implemented.

Counselling Implications

Findings from this study have important implications for counsellors, parents, clinicians, teachers, and other significant persons responsible for the well-being of adolescents. According to Schuster et al (2002), the beginning of adolescents engaging in sexual experience and behaviour with partners is not marked by a single act but rather it involves a range of activities that should be guided to avoid misconceptions that could lead to serious damages on adolescents present and future well-being because of ignorance and misinformation from peers, cultural backgrounds, beliefs and so on.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study and the discussions that followed, the following conclusions were drawn. Students of FCT COE, Zuba are unanimous in their perception of the types of social behaviour prevalent among adolescents irrespective of their age or gender difference. In line with the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

Sex education should be introduced as a viable and compulsory course in our education curriculum, especially in higher institutions. The indebt knowledge of sexuality education will prevent the youth from undesirable sexual behaviour. Youths should be taught about human anatomy from as early as five to ten years, emphasizing the changes they are likely to experience in their body. Sex education programmes such as lectures, symposia, seminars, and public enlightenment campaigns where adolescents can be given information about sex and sexuality education should be designed.

Further, an atmosphere where youths can be free to ask questions about sex and sexuality should be created. This will enable them to understand sex better and they will stay out of trouble as regards making decisions about sexual issues and behaviour. As counsellors, teachers, and parents, there is a need to source different appropriate information about sex and sexuality and make it available to the youths. Parents and significant others should be encouraged not to shun but always answer questions from the youths regarding sex no matter how appropriate or inappropriate. The youths and their parents should be provided with adequate guidance services.

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